

EURAF submission to the MFF Consultation

Version 1. 6.5.25 - 10.5281/zenodo.15351655

Integrating agriculture, forestry, energy and climate planning at a regional scale

EURAF Submission to the [consultation](#) on the Multiannual Financial Framework -

1. Introduction

EURAF notes that the current multiannual financial framework (MFF) – the EU’s long-term budget – runs until the end of 2027, and that in 2025, the Commission aims to adopt comprehensive proposals for the post-2027 multiannual financial framework, and for the next generation of funding programmes.

In the Political Guidelines for the 2024-2029 European Commission ([Jul 2024](#)) the Commission promises to work towards a “*simpler, more focused and responsive long-term budget that reflects the European strategic priorities with the ambition to be an ‘Investment Commission’*”, being:

- ***Simpler in the way it works*** – with fewer programmes and a plan for each country linking key reforms with investment, and focusing on our joint priorities, including promoting economic, social and territorial cohesion.
- ***Focused on things that matter most***, in areas where it can achieve more than Member States acting alone - requiring a careful assessment both of what has worked well in the past and what could be improved in the future - with a focus on simplicity and flexibility, speed and strategic focus.
- ***Based on evidence and views from all interested parties*** on how to make the very most of every euro of the EU budget - including cohesion policy, common agricultural policy, fisheries and maritime policies, home affairs and Trans-European Networks.

The Land Sector is far from meeting its 2040 net-zero targets and a **radical rethink of the integration of trees into agricultural landscapes** is needed as soon as possible - with a particular focus on those parts of Europe which are agricultural tree deserts, and where trees can make the most impact on carbon sequestration.

A “just transition”¹ of the CAP has been discussed for a long time, with many arguing for a fit-for-purpose agricultural policy in the next MFF, which is aligned with agroecological solutions and climate justice, and where the agri-food system works with nature but ensures that farmers get fair prices for their work, with fairer market organisation and better collection and sharing of data across the sector. The cross-sector *Strategic Dialogue on the Future of EU Agriculture* ([Sep 24](#)), and DGAGRI *Vision for Agriculture and Food* ([Feb 25](#)) both contain initiatives which EURAF has welcomed in our document *Agroforestry Futures for the EU* ([Feb 25](#)).

EURAF aligns itself with the common position of EU Environmental NGOs (e.g. [Food Policy Coalition](#)) likely to be submitted to the MFF consultation, including the following points ...

1. **Public subsidies should bring with them a base level of responsibilities (“conditionality”)**, and options for additional incentives for farmers who produce quality food while preserving nature, soil, water and landscapes and contributing to climate mitigation and adaptation. Nature-positive, organic, agro-ecological and agroforestry-based farming are important, as is the maintenance of high standards of animal-welfare, biodiversity, landscape diversity, social-cohesion and labour-standards. A progressive move is needed away from untargeted area-based payments towards payments which reward measurable environment, climate and social benefits.
2. **Sufficient public funding should be allocated to incentivising and de-risking the “just transition”**, for example by supporting crop diversification, agro-ecological infrastructures, agroforestry, mixed-farming, areas with natural constraints, extensive pastoral systems, circular systems for energy self-sustainability, improved animal welfare; cooperative farming options, land access tools, independent advisory and incubation services, as well as top-quality jobs.

¹ Defined by the [EESC](#) as “.. addressing social, environmental and economic aspects coherently, adopting a holistic, coordinated and integrated approach. The just transition should be based on the principles of distributive justice, recognition, participation, environmental and climate ambition, human rights, and ‘leaving no one behind’”;

3. **Public funding should be available for post-farmgate value chains**, including cooperative infrastructure, local processing facilities and logistics networks adapted to diverse, agroecological farming models investments in the activities of the agri-food sector beyond the farm gate, e.g. to support the development of new value chains.
4. **Generational renewal is important**, and access to agricultural policy funds should be facilitated for young farmers and new entrants of all ages and backgrounds especially women and underrepresented groups. Extra support could be provided to those who want to engage in organic or agroecological farming, with targeted instruments for land access, farm succession, cooperative farm creation, and long-term tenure security.
5. **Agricultural funds should be distributed more fairly to those who need it the most** - with increased benefits to smaller farms rather than big holdings. Degressivity, capping and redistributive payments should be employed by all Member States. Small and medium-sized farms are key to maintaining vibrant rural territories, biodiversity and food security, and to protecting landscape features and biodiversity, yet they have been disappearing at a dramatic pace. It is also necessary to counteract and reverse the harmful effects of land concentration, land grabbing and speculative land acquisitions.
6. **Rules for spending of EU funds by Member States should not permit a race to the bottom on social and environmental goals in agriculture**. A common, result-based, framework including clear objectives towards which progress can be tracked, should ensure the delivery of ambitious outcomes on socio-economic aspects, decent work and labour standards, GHG emission reductions, nature and biodiversity protection and recovery, animal welfare, etc.

However, successive cycles of consultation on the CAP have promised most of the above actions, and have failed to deliver on them. Nor has the CAP helped deliver climate targets. Deeper reform is needed.

Reviews of the environmental ([CoA 2024](#)) or climate ([CoA 2021](#)) impact of the CAP show major failings, and an increasing disconnect between actions planned in the CAP and those supported with national funds or EU regional programmes. For example, more and more countries (including France and Germany) are funding forestry outside the CAP, and not providing metrics to DGAGRI on these activities. Even when the metrics are provided, Member States have consistently shown themselves unable to deliver on their modest afforestation and agroforestation targets. They took little action to modify their CAP Strategic Plans to meet their targets in National Energy and Climate Plans or to follow advice on making these modifications from DG CLIMA ([May 23](#)). Two DG AGRI-commissioned reports ([Oct 18](#) and [Nov 24](#)) show that very little attention is given to quantifying the climate impact of individual CAP Policies, despite the optimistic assumptions made. One of the few climate-positive measures - maintaining a 3-4% target for landscape features (including woody landscape features) in GAEC8 was abandoned in the 2024 “simplification” round, with no regard to the climate impact. The 3 billion “*additional*” trees programme ([DG Env](#)) has recorded less than 25 million “*additional*” trees planted half way through the decade ([MapMyTree Portal](#)) and the Commission is unable to report on how many “*business as usual trees*” are being planted by Member States in the current CAP (EURAF [Policy Briefing #70](#)).

The time is now to dismantle the current structure of the CAP and undertake a radical review of delivery models and impact metrics with a GENUINE focus on meeting the land sector net zero target by 2040.

2. Integrated agriculture, forestry and climate budgets at regional scale (“Agroforestry Max”)

Considering that:

1. Forests cover 40% of the EU land surface², yet they accounted for less than 1% of planned CAP Expenditure in the 2014-22 period.³
2. 85kha of agroforestry planting was originally planned by MS in the 2014-22 period but less than 5kha was achieved.
3. Nine Member States have no plans for afforestation or agroforestation in their CAP budgets (AT, BE-W, EE, FI, FR, IE, FR, LU, SE) and 6 more plan to establish less than 400ha over the 6-year period (CY, ST, SL, MT, DE, BE-F).⁴
4. Many countries are withdrawing their forestry expenditure from the CAP (IE, NL, FI, SE, FR, DE) and do not provide forestry metrics to the Commission.

² Compilation of Table 4.1 in national GHG Inventories for 2024 showing forest land 39.8%, cropland 28.4%, grassland 17.0%, wetland 5.7%, settlements 6.8% and other land 2.2%

³ Special Report 21 “EU funding for biodiversity and climate change in EU Forests” ([Court of Auditors 2021](#))

⁴ EU Agri Food Results Indicator [dashboard](#)

5. The recent DGAGRI *Strategic Dialogue* and *Vision*⁵ documents make little mention of forestry or agroforestry.
6. The new European Board on Agriculture and Food (EBAF) has no representation of forestry organisations amongst its 30 non governmental members. It may perpetuate a business as usual approach.⁶
7. The majority of Joint Research Centre agricultural foresight studies⁷ fail to mention agroforestry or trees outside forests.
8. The EU will collectively miss its 2030 LULUCF carbon sequestration of -310 Mt Co2 by around 30-40 Mt CO2, because of increasing pressures on forests and stable or rising emissions from agriculture.⁸
9. The draft Forest Monitoring Strategy⁹ does not mention Trees outside Forests despite the fact that the crown area of these trees, in some countries¹⁰, can be as much as 30% of the total tree cover.
10. There are around 93 Mha of cropland and agricultural land in the EU-27 with no tree cover¹¹, and these hectares are mainly on mineral soils where tree planting would have the biggest benefit..

Extensive research, coupled with the practical experience of EURAF members across Europe ([TP Organics 2025](#)), backs up the claim that agroforestry has a vital role in helping meet the goals of the DGAGRI *Vision for Agriculture and Food*. But that *Vision* focuses primarily on “agriculture and food”: not forestry (*no mention of 3 billion trees or the Forest Monitoring Directive*), not resilient ecosystems (*no mention of the Nature Restoration Regulation*¹²), not the soil resource (*no mention of the Soil Monitoring Directive*), not water quality or adaptation to climate change (*Water Resilience Strategy and new Adaptation Plan are missing from the Commission's 2025 WorkProgramme*). The previous emphasis on the land sector meeting its 2030 climate targets, and 2040 climate neutrality, is replaced by compromise wording which focuses on the need for “*competitiveness, food security and strengthening the bioeconomy*”.

The omission of agroforestry in the *Vision* is particularly disappointing in view of its recognition in high-level experts panels, such as the IPCC Special Report on Climate and Land ([IPCC 2019](#)) and the European Scientific Advisory Board on Climate Change ([ESABCC 2024](#) & [2025](#)). EURAF ([2024](#)) has consistently emphasised the potential of agroforestry to contribute to 2040 climate targets and to resilient and biodiverse lands and ecosystems. Yet only 9 MS have implemented agroforestry interventions, and these at a very modest scale.

Also, the *Vision* suggests a range of new initiatives without mentioning similar attempts in the past which have failed or stalled. These include the Farm Sustainability Platform (FaST), the GreenData4All Initiative and compliance by Member States with the, almost twenty-years-old, INSPIRE Directive (2007/2/EC) for open access to geospatial data linked to public funding.

GHG emissions from the EU land sector are not decreasing ([EU National Inventory Document 13.12.24](#) & Common Reporting Tables, [28.4.25](#))¹³ despite recent optimistic assumptions on the potential of the current CAP ([Monitoring Helpdesk 2024](#)). Climate change mitigation seems low on the list of priorities of MS when Strategic Plans are written or modified.

It is clear that many policymakers still view agriculture and forestry in separate siloes, with agricultural trees falling through the gap between them. Both sets of policies should be given maximum subsidiarity, but with an emphasis on closer integration and efficient reporting and planning based on climate mitigation and adaptation targets as main priorities.

EURAF welcomed (“[Agroforestry Futures in the EU](#)”) the **following ten commitments** in the DGAGRI Vision for Agriculture and Food (in bold), **BUT** with caveats:

1. **Fertile land is limited in the EU and should be protected.** **BUT** well-designed agroforestry systems protect and improve soil fertility through enhanced nutrient cycling without compromising crop/pasture or livestock productivity. In addition, trees can provide multiple ecosystem services as well as tree products

⁵ The [Strategic Dialogue on the Future of Agriculture](#) did stress the need for collaboration between the agriculture and forestry sectors but included agroforestry only 3 times.. The [Vision for Agriculture and Food](#) mentioned forestry only 4 times and agroforestry not at all.

⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/expert-groups-register/screen/expert-groups/consult?lang=en&groupID=3976>

⁷ Scenarios for EU Rural Areas 2040 ([6.7.21](#));

⁸ European Climate Neutrality Observatory - [progress tracker](#))

⁹ <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-a-european-green-deal/file-eu-forest-observation-reporting-and-data-collection>

¹⁰ For example in [England](#)

¹¹ EURAF Press Release Feb 2024. “Agroforestry - vital to Europe's land emission neutrality”

¹² EURAF agrees with the MFF submission of the EEB that a Nature Restoration Fund of around €15 should be established.

¹³ A [trend apparent](#) in most OECD countries

- (e.g., quality timber, firewood, biochar, fruits, nuts, fodder), which can substantially diversify farm income. Agroforestry needs greater encouragement
2. **A “Farm Sustainability Compass” will streamline reporting and reduce administrative burdens for farmers, allowing them to monitor and record sustainability data only once, while gradually adopting more sustainable practices and attracting new sources of financing.** BUT, emphasis is needed on building the Sustainability Compass around the CAP Land Parcel Information System (LPIS), with data on agricultural trees and landscape features collected at a scale where tree planting initiatives and nature based solutions implemented by individual farmers can be rewarded and integrated into future carbon farming schemes.
 3. **An EU Observatory on Farmland will potentially enhance transparency and cooperation in domains such as land transactions and transfers of land use rights.** BUT the Vision fails to emphasise the role of forest land and tenant farmers¹⁴. We emphasise that the CAP Land Parcel Identification system should be integrated with national cadastral systems to provide open access to a 100% mapping of rural and peri urban land..
 4. **Nature Credits are commendable** BUT have been discussed for years with little progress. Environmental impact metrics are, so-far, inadequate to support any form of “payment by results” - not to mention that they are viewed by the WTO as ineligible under GATT Annex 2 Rules. The Common European Agricultural Data Space has to help in collecting and harmonising the data needed.
 5. **A toolbox of tailored measures is needed to support the sector and regions in their efforts to reduce emissions.** BUT, while models and maps (Figs 1 & 2) have been developed to show regions and areas where “tree deserts” exist, and where even small areas of tree planting or woodland restoration can have the biggest benefit, there are few available mechanisms to focus tree-planting where the need is greatest.
 6. **Renewable energy production in agriculture is vital.** BUT, while agroforestry and agri-voltaics can provide biomass, electricity, syngas and methane for neighbouring communities, there is little evidence of successful CAP/regional/private integrated funding schemes for these options.
 7. **Carbon farming is emerging as an additional source of income.** BUT, the voluntary carbon farming schemes, being developed through the CRCF Regulation, are likely to be small and slow to catch on. The “agri-ETS” under discussion in DGCLIMA should be implemented soon to bring about a real change by 2040. A statutory carbon farming scheme of this type will also be needed to extend energy accounting to agriculture and forestry imports via the EU Carbon Borders Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM).
 8. The *Vision* promises “**long-term support for the livestock sector, with an emphasis on traditional extensive grazing and animal welfare**”, BUT the importance of silvopastoralism in these traditional systems is not mentioned. EURAF’s “[Brno Declaration](#)” called for 11.2 million ha of new agroforestry, of which 2 million ha is for new silvopastoralism, plus greater support for restoring existing parkland systems, and an emphasis on delivering the Commission’s plans for 3 billion additional trees by 2030.
 9. **The *Vision* emphasises an ambitious investment agenda linked to the “one health approach”.** BUT EURAF has been lobbying for several years for agroforestry and sustainable agriculture to be included in the Sustainable Finance Taxonomy, with no apparent movement. Agroforestry and nature based solutions to climate change have a major role to play in the EU’s proposed Competitiveness Compass, and private investment should be strongly encouraged.
 10. Finally, the *Vision* lists **environmental goals of resilient ecosystems, maintenance of soils, fight against pests and diseases, pollination of crops, water quality and availability, clean air and climate conditions.** BUT, although agroforestry contributes handsomely to all these priorities it has not been encouraged sufficiently by Member States in the present and past CAP. It is time to move from traditional area-based payments to a system of public income support to smaller farmers, environmental and climate payment by results, linked to private investment, and a more comprehensive set of objective environmental, social and regional indicators which evaluate the success of each intervention.

Agriculture, forestry, environment, carbon and climate funding should therefore be integrated at regional level with maximum subsidiarity for these regions, balanced by an emphasis on open data with robust, frequent and harmonised reporting of results. The present structure of the CAP should be dismantled.

¹⁴ Almost 50% of EU Utilised Agricultural Area is rented (Farm Structure Survey [2020](#)): BG 77, SK 74, MT 74, CZ 73, EL 61, LV 55, LT 54, FR 51, BE 50, HU 50, AT 49, **EU (average %) 46**, NL 45, SL 44, IT 43, DE 40, CY 39, FI 34, SE 33, EL 32, DK 31, RO 26, ES 25, IE 23, HR 22, LU 21, PT 20, PL 18.. which greatly constraints opportunities for agricultural tree planting .. unless the **structure of EU leasehold is addressed**.

Figure 1. Tree cover density (% tree cover in 100 m pixels) in cropland/grassland in the 39 EEA countries. The deep red areas are priority planting areas where tree cover density is particularly low. They are usually on mineral soils where agroforestry will make the greatest contribution to carbon sequestration. Source: Copernicus tree cover density 2018 superimposed on CORINE agricultural land 2018. Each pixel in this map covers 1ha.

Figure 2: Trees outside Forests (green) in England , using information from LIDAR imagery. Also showing small blocks of forest (grey) in the National Forest Inventory (minimum size of 0.1ha)- [Forest Research 2025](#)